

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A YOUNG MALE WITH SPLENIC VEIN AND SMV
THROMBOSIS AND JAK 22 MUTATION**

Dr Asif Islam, Dr Zainab Younus

Article Received: August 2020 **Accepted:** September 2020 **Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

We are reporting a case of a 22-year-old man who suffers from SMV thrombosis. At the initial stage, he complains about abdominal pain, nausea, and poor appetite. We took a proper medical history of the patient and analyzed white blood cells for the analysis of JAK2 mutation. Furthermore, abdominal ultrasound was performed to analyze the bulky pancreas. We observed a few enlarged 0.8cm mesenteric lymph nodes. On the other hand, however, no observation of osseous lesion.

Keywords:

Abdominal ultrasound, Superior mesenteric vein, JAK2 mutation, nausea, Mesenteric lymph nodes.

Corresponding author:**Asif Islam,**

QR code

Please cite this article in press Asif Islam et al, A Young Male With Splenic Vein And SMV Thrombosis And Jak 22 Mutation., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(10).

INTRODUCTION:

Splanchnic vein thrombosis (SVT) is a disorder that involves venous thrombus within the portal vein (PVT), superior mesenteric vein, splenic vein¹. The presence of JAK2 mutation is responsible for the formation of thrombosis among patients. Diagnosis of thrombocytosis among adults is possible after the analysis of JAK2 mutation and bone marrow biopsy². In 2008, the World health organization revealed that JAK2 mutation is a major criterion in the diagnosis of thrombosis³. Superior mesenteric vein thrombosis disorder is considered as an abdominal emergency due to the high rate of intestinal infarction in case of late diagnosis. superior mesenteric vein disorder is a rare disease with a high mortality rate^{4,5}. Approximately 5-15% of cases of acute mesenteric ischemia arise due to superior mesenteric vein⁶. Little awareness, low incidence rate, and non-specific abdominal symptoms are major obstacles in diagnosis⁷. However, in new diagnostic images modalities help in the identification and management of disease before laparotomies⁸. Studies revealed that out of 5000 patients, 1 patient was diagnosed with acute superior mesenteric venous thrombosis (ASMVT) whereas among every 1000 patients 1 patient of ASMVT admits into the emergency department⁹. It was first identified by Eliot and other researchers and considered that it may arise due to the intestinal infarction¹⁰.

Few studies are conducted to explore the frequency of JAK2 mutation along with the superior mesenteric vein among the patients with splenic thrombosis. This study aims to identify the high-risk patients of SMV thrombosis with the help of JAK2 mutation analysis.

- **Case history:**

A 22-year-young male presented to the ER with complaints of abdominal pain, poor appetite and nausea along with occasional vomiting. Pain, described as constant and dull in nature without radiation more in left hypochondrium region, started 1

week earlier. In addition to this, he has altered bowel habits mainly constipation (type 2 as per Bristol stool chart) for which he took laxatives. However, he denied bloody, or bilious vomiting, melena, or hematochezia. Chronic problem included gastroesophageal reflux disease from the last one year and he used to take PPIs and Gastroprotective agents off and on. He was tested for H-Pylori infection that turned out to be negative. He has significant unintentional weight loss (almost 12 kg) over the period of two months. He had similar episode of abdominal pain 1 year back for which he underwent diagnostic workup but that turned out to be inconclusive. Family history was insignificant. The patient denied heavy alcohol use and history of smoking/ drug addiction but he gives history of hakeem medication.

- **Physical examination results**

Physical examination demonstrated thin lean patient young patient with obvious temporal wasting. Mild abdominal tenderness more in left hypochondrium without peritoneal signs. He had palpable spleen 5cm below left costal margin moving with respiration and non-tender. No evidence of free fluid in peritoneal cavity.

- **Results of pathological tests and other investigations**

Complete blood count (CBC) revealed a red blood cell count of $6.90 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$ (reference range: $4.3-5.9 \times 10^9/\mu\text{L}$), hemoglobin of 16.3 g/dL (reference range: 13.5-17.5 g/dL), hematocrit of 54.0% (reference range: 41%-53%), and platelet count of $923 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ (reference range: $150-400 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$). Other laboratory findings of note included a white blood count of $10.1 \times 10^9/\text{L}$ (reference range: $4.5-11.0 \times 10^9/\text{L}$), aspartate aminotransferase of 53 U/L (reference range: 8-20 U/L), alanine aminotransferase of 48 U/L (reference range: 8-20 U/L), and total bilirubin of 0.61 mg/dL (reference range: 0.1-1 mg/dL). Serum amylase and lipase were within normal limits.

Reports attached below;

evercare HOSPITAL LAHORE **IDC**
Diagnostic Partner

D1 Commercial, Nespak Cooperative Housing Society (NECHS), Lahore UAN: (051) 111 000 432
 Name: **Mr. Ali Nawaz / Evc000007808**
 MRN / PIN: C-2-58617 / 2001-01-031096 Age/Gender: 22 yrs(M)
 Ref. By: Dr. Akif Dilshad Ref.No: ECL 19D

Visit Date: 13-Jan-2020 8:26 pm **Final Report** Report Date: 13-Jan-2020 8:53 pm

Test Name	Results	*Last Available Results	Unit	Reference Ranges
Chemistry				
Liver Function Tests				
Total Bilirubin	0.61		mg/dL	Adults: 0.1 - 1.1 Newborn: <10
S.G.P.T. (ALT)	48		U/L	5 - 55
S.G.O.T. (AST)	53		U/L	9 - 40
Alkaline Phosphatase	160		U/L	Adults: 30 - 115 Up to 15 Years: < 345 15 - 17 Years: < 483
Gamma GT	94		U/L	Male: < 55 Female: <38
Albumin	3.99		g/dL	3.0 - 5.0

Please correlate clinically.
 Please Note: Test (s) are performed on the state - of - the - art ARCHITECT MODULAR C8200 from Abbott Diagnostics, U.S.A

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Printed By: simon.guitar [ECL] @ 19-Feb-2020 1:43:21 pm Page 1 of 1

evercare HOSPITAL LAHORE **IDC**
Diagnostic Partner

D1 Commercial, Nespak Cooperative Housing Society (NECHS), Lahore UAN: (051) 111 000 432
 Name: **Mr. Ali Nawaz / Evc000007808**
 MRN / PIN: C-2-58617 / 2001-01-030926 Age/Gender: 22 yrs(M)
 Ref. By: Dr. Akif Dilshad Ref.No: ECL 19D

Visit Date: 13-Jan-2020 7:29 pm **Final Report** Report Date: 13-Jan-2020 7:40 pm

Test Name	Results	*Last Available Results	Unit	Reference Ranges
Hematology				
Complete Blood Picture (CBC)				
WBC Count	10,100		/mm ³	4000 - 11,000
RBC Count	6.90		mil/mm ³	4.5-6.0
Haemoglobin	16.3		g/dL	14.0 - 18.0
Hematocrit	54		%	40 - 50
MCV	79		fl	80 - 95
MCH	24		pg	27 - 31
MCHC	30		g/dL	32 - 36
RDW-CV	16		%	11 - 16
Platelet Count	923,600		/mm ³	140,000 - 425,000
Differential Count				
Neutrophils	63		%	50 - 70
Lymphocytes	18		%	25 - 40
Monocytes	12		%	2 - 10
Eosinophils	07		%	0 - 4
Bands	00		%	0 - 5
Absolute Count				
Absolute Neutrophil Count	6342		/mm ³	2500-7000
Absolute Lymphocyte Count	1635		/mm ³	1500-4000
Absolute Monocyte Count	1231		/mm ³	200-1000
Absolute Eosinophil Count	682		/mm ³	100-500
E.S.R.	05		mm/1Hr	Male: 0 - 15 Female: 0 - 20

Eosinophilia.
 Thrombocytosis.
 Hypochromic Microcytic RBC.
 Please Note: Test (s) are performed on state - of - the - art Cell Dyn Ruby, automated 5 part hematology analyzer from Abbott Diagnostics, USA.

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Due to acute abdominal symptoms, the initial study performed was abdominal ultrasound which showed bulky pancreas with heterogenous echogenicity. Hepatic part of portal vein is of normal caliber and is patent with sluggish hepato-fugal flow. Spleno-portal confluence is compressed and not outlined. Organized thrombus in Superior mesenteric vein. Moderate splenomegaly with perihilar spenicule. SEE THE ATTACHMENT BELOW FOR DETAILS;

Name	Mr. Ali Nawaz / Evc0000007808				
Age/Gender	22 yr(s) / M	MRN	C-2-58617		
Ref. By	Dr. Akif Dilshad	Report Date	13-Jan-2020	Reg. Date	13-Jan-2020 08:42 pm

ULTRASOUND ABDOMEN

Pancreas appears bulky and shows ill defined outline with heterogeneous echogenicity. Echogenic soft tissue with pancreatic echogenicity is encasing the celiac axis vessels and CBD which is of normal caliber. Although not classic but autoimmune pancreatitis and sequelae may be considered. CT is suggested for additional evaluation

Hepatic part of the portal vein is of normal caliber and is patent however shows sluggish hepatofugal flow. Splenoportal confluence is compressed and not outlined.

There is organized thrombus in the superior mesenteric vein. Multiple enlarged mesenteric lymph nodes are also noted.

Spleen (17 cm) is enlarged. No focal lesion seen. Splenic hilar 1.7 cm splenicule is noted.

Liver span (12.2 cm) shows homogenous parenchyma and smooth surface. No focal lesion or dilated biliary ducts are seen.

Gall bladder is fairly distended and shows mild diffuse wall edema; no calculus is seen. CBD 5 mm is normal and no calculus seen in visualized part.

Right kidney measures 9.5 x 4.1 cm (Parenchymal thickness is 1.6 cm)

Left kidney measures 9.4 x 3.3 cm (Parenchymal thickness is 1.6 cm)

Both kidneys show fairly normal parenchymal echoes and CMD. No calculus or hydronephrosis seen on either side. Urinary Bladder appears normal. Prostate is not enlarged. No ascites or significant para-aortic lymphadenopathy.

IMPRESSION:

- Bulky Pancreas with ill defined outline and heterogeneous echogenicity
- Echogenic soft tissue with pancreatic echogenicity is encasing the celiac axis vessels and

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Page 1 of 2

Name	Mr. Ali Nawaz / Evc0000007808				
Age/Gender	22 yr(s) / M	MRN	C-2-58617		
Ref. By	Dr. Akif Dilshad	Report Date	13-Jan-2020	Reg. Date	13-Jan-2020 08:42 pm

CBD which is of normal caliber - Autoimmune pancreatitis and sequelae may be considered; CT is suggested for additional assessment.

- Hepatic part of the portal vein is of normal caliber and is patent with sluggish hepatofugal flow
- Splenoportal confluence is compressed and not outlined.
- Organized thrombus in the superior mesenteric vein
- Multiple enlarged mesenteric lymph nodes with no evident bowel wall thickening except for non specific edema
- Moderate splenomegaly with perihilar splenicule

 Dr. Faisal Ehsan Cheema
 Associate Consultant Radiologist
 MBBS, Dpt Card, MS; (Nuclear Medicine),
 FRCR (Radiology), EDiR

For referring physician and/or to furnish a second opinion, hard copy images have been handed over to patient. Radiology image interpretation may vary from radiologists to radiologists. Repeat study with variable radiation dose, position, contrast or additional viewing on other modality before and after clinical completion may be needed. For any query or confusion, don't hesitate to contact our reporting doctor or diagnostic center.

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Page 2 of 2

Doppler USG abdomen showed organized thrombus in SMV, extrahepatic portal vein and splenic vein.

IDC Diagnostic Partner			
Name	Mr. Ali Nawaz / Evc0000007808		
Age/Gender	22 yr(s) / M	MRN	C-2-58617
Ref. By	Dr. Akif Dilshad	Report Date	20-Jan-2020
		Reg. Date	20-Jan-2020 08:12 pm

DOPPLER ULTRASOUND ABDOMEN

Intrahepatic Portal vein 7 mm is patent shows flow reversal with reduced flow velocity flow.
 Hepatic veins are patent and show normal respiratory phasicity.
 IVC shows normal caliber with preserved respiratory phasicity.
 Superior mesenteric vein shows luminal echoes suggesting organized thrombosis through its traceable length.
 Extrahepatic portal vein and splenic vein show no flow signals likely of thrombosis.
 Collaterals are noted at porta hepatis and in the right mesentery.
 Superior Mesenteric artery ostial velocity is normal.

IMPRESSION:

- Organized thrombus in the SMV, extrahepatic portal vein and splenic vein
- Collaterals in the porta hepatis and in the right mesentery

Dr. Faisal Ehsan Cheema
 Associate Consultant Radiologist
 MBBS, Dipl Card, MSc (Nuclear Medicine),
 FCPS (Radiology), EDIR

For referring physician and or to furnish a second opinion, hard copy images have been handed over to patient. Radiology image interpretation may vary from radiologists to radiologist. Repeat study with variable radiation dose, position, contrast or additional viewing on other modality before and after clinical correlation may be needed. For any query or confusion, don't hesitate to contact our reporting doctor or diagnostic center.

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Protein C 84.2 (reference range 70-140) and Protein S 90.8 (reference range 55-130). Factor V laiden mutation not detected.

Visit Date: 21-Jan-2020 5:00 pm	Final Report		Report Date: 23-Jan-2020 3:47 p
Test Name	Results	*Last Available Results	Unit Reference Rang

Special Pathology

	21-Jan-2020		
Factor V Leiden mutation	Not Detected		
** Performed by PCR			

Comments:

Factor V assay is a qualitative genotyping test for the rapid detection of factor alleles from sodium citrate or EDTA anticoagulated whole blood. Factor V Leiden mutation provides an aid in the diagnosis of suspected thrombophilia. The test is performed on the Cepheid Genexpert system and provides result for factor V mutation.

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Lahore UAN: (051) 111 000 432

IDC
Diagnostic Partner

Name: Mr. Ali Nawaz /Evc0000007808
MRN / PIN: C-2-58617 / 2001-01-053231
Ref. By: Dr. Akif Dilshad

Age/Gender: 22 yr(s)/M
Ref.No: OPD

Visit Date: 21-Jan-2020 5:00 pm	Final Report		Report Date: 25-Jan-2020 12:02 pm
Test Name	Results	*Last Available Results	Unit Reference Ranges

Special Hematology

	21-Jan-2020		
Protein C	84.2		% 70-140
Protein S (AC)	90.8		% 55-130

Note:

Protein S: is a vitamin K dependent protein and acts as a cofactor of activated Protein C in the proteolytic inactivation of Factor Va & VIIIa, thereby stimulating Coagulations-Inhibition effect.

Causes of diminished protein S activities are:

- 1- hereditary protein S deficiency.
- 2- hepatic disorders.
- 3- treatment with L-asparaginase.
- 4- pregnancy.
- 5- oral contraceptives.
- 6- estrogen therapy.
- 7- elevated plasma levels of C4b Binding Protein as an acute phase reaction.

The final diagnosis made up on triphasic CT scan findings are as below ;

Fig; Arrow pointing out to thrombus in splenic vein

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(051) 111 000 432

Name	Mr. Ali Nawaz /Evc0000007808			 * 2 0 0 1 - 0 1 - 0 3 3 7 4 6 *
Age/Gender	22 yr(s) / M	MRN	C-2-58617	
Ref. By	Dr. Akif Dilshad	Report Date	15-Jan-2020	Reg. Date 14-Jan-2020 06:55 pm

CT ABDOMEN (TRIPHASIC)

CLINICAL INFO: H/O abdomen pain, significant weight loss and occasional vomiting.

TECHNIQUE: 1 mm reconstructed images from a scan performed on **Philips 128 slice CT scan Ingenuity Core** (with low radiation & high definition mode) reviewed on workstation. Non-enhanced and post contrast tri-phasic/dynamic CT abdomen performed in arterial, venous and delayed phases.

Comparison: Ultrasound of the patient performed on 30th January 2020 is reviewed at the time of reporting.

FINDINGS:

The liver is not enlarged and demonstrates smooth surfaces with normal parenchymal enhancement. No arterialized hepatic lesion is seen.

Spleen is markedly enlarged and shows lobulated margins, measures approximately 18 cm in craniocaudal dimension, measured on reformatted coronal images. It shows multiple peripheral hypodense areas in keeping with infarcts. An approximately 2 cm splenunculus is noted at its lower pole.

There is extensive thrombosis of portal vein, its confluence with long segment extension into SMV. Splenic artery and veins are not opacified, likely thrombosed.

There is long segment extensive thickening and enhancement of CBD, starting from its confluence till ampulla with abrupt cut off in ampullary region. This shows multifocal areas of stenosis. Large mass like tissue surrounding CBD in porta hepatic region and extending in pancreatoduodenal groove, appears inseparable from head and uncinata process. No pancreatic duct dilatation. Pancreatic body and tail appears within normal limits.

Gallbladder, bilateral adrenals and both kidneys are enhancing normally. Mesenteric stranding is also demonstrated. Few enlarged mesenteric lymph nodes are seen, largest measures 0.8 cm in short axis. Visualized small and large bowel shows reactive thickening and long segment collapsed transverse colon. No size significant pelvic side wall, paraaortic lymphadenopathy. No abdominopelvic ascites.

Sections through the lung basis grossly appear unremarkable. No suspicious nodule is seen. No pleural effusion.

No destructive osseous lesion is seen.

IMPRESSION:

Long segment enhancing thickening of CBD, from its confluence till ampulla with multifocal

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Page 1 of 2.

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In case of query/discrepancy, the referring physician may contact reporting doctor within 48 hrs for detailed discussion. Not Valid for court.

Evercare Hospital, Shahrah Nazaria-e- Pakistan, Near Wapda Town Roundabout NECHS, Lahore

Call: 0511-111-432 UAN: 051-111-257-222 www.evc.net.pk

JAK 2 V617F mutation detected by PCR confirming chronic myeloproliferative neoplasm.

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D1 Commercial, Nespak Cooperative Housing Society (NECHS),
Lahore UAN: (051) 111 000 432

Name: Mr. Ali Nawaz /Evc0000007808
MRN / PIN: C-2-58617 / 2001-01-053231 **Age/Gender:** 22 yr(s)/M
Ref. By: Dr. Akif Dilshad **Ref.No:** OPD

Visit Date: 21-Jan-2020 5:00 pm **Final Report** Report Date: 03-Feb-2020 6:39 pm

Test Name	Results	*Last Available Results	Unit	Reference Ranges
Molecular Biology				
		21-Jan-2020		
JAK2 MUTATION	JAK 2 Mutation detected			

Method:

Genomic DNA is extracted from WBCs and analysed for V617F Mutation by polymerase chain reaction.

[Tests performed by The Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi. * Please see attached report (s)]

آغا خان یونیورسٹی ہسپتال، کراچی

The Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi

CAP
ACCREDITED
COLLEGE of AMERICAN PATHOLOGISTS

Stadium Road, P.O. Box 3500,
Karachi - 74800, Pakistan
G 11 Markaz Collection Unit Tel:(051) 2362601

Medical Record # : L23173791 (IG11387)

Patient Name : 2001-01-.053231

Specimen ID : 2020:MO0234R

Clinical Information / Comments:

sdd2 sample recvied from idc

Age / Gender : 22Y / Male

Location : ISB4

Requesting Physician : IDC

Account # : C30230466 - OSR

Requested on : 22/01/2020 - 20:36

Collected on : 22/01/2020 - 20:36

Reported on : 31/01/2020 - 16:44

SOURCE: BLOOD

JAK2 V617F Mutation Detection by PCR [Final

Clinical Diagnosis: Chronic Myeloproliferative Neoplasms

Result: Positive

Clinical interpretation:

1. Positive mutation status is highly suggestive of a myeloproliferative neoplasm (MPN), but must be correlated with clinical and other laboratory features for definitive diagnosis.

2. Detection of the JAK2 V617F is useful to help establish the diagnosis of MPN. However, a negative JAK2 V617F result does not indicate the absence of MPN.

Method:

Total DNA is extracted from patient's blood is analyzed for JAK2 V617F gene, amplified by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using a sequence specific primer to the JAK 2 target determined by end product analysis.

Clinical Information:

1. BCR-ABL1-negative NPM frequently harbor an acquired single nucleotide mutation in JAK2 (Exon 14) characterized as 1849G> T; p. Val617Phe (V617F).

[JAK, GenBank ID 3717 & MIM 147796] which is located on short arm of chromosome 9 (9p24)

2. The JAK2 V617F is present in 95% to 98% of polycythemia vera (PV), and 50% to 60% of primary myelofibrosis (PMF) and essential thrombocythemia (ET).

Comments:

1. A positive result is not specific for a particular subtype of MPN and clinico-pathologic correlation is necessary in all cases.

2. A negative result does not exclude the presence of a MPN or other neoplastic process.

3. In rare cases, a mutation other than the V617F may be present in an area that interferes with primer or probe binding and cause a false-negative result.

4. This is a Laboratory Developed Test where the performance characteristics have

Continued 2

Dr. Zahra Hasan
PhD, UJK
Professor

Dr. Tariq Moattar
MS, Mphi, PhD
Professor

Dr. Zeeshan Ansar Ahmed
MBBS, FCPS (Hematology)
Assistant Professor

Dr. Kiran Iqbal
MSc (Microbiology), PhD
Senior Instructor

Dr. Asghar Nasir
MSc, PhD (UJK)
Assistant Professor

Dr. Neja Ghanchi
MS, PhD
Assistant Professor

- Treatment plan
 - Actual outcome.
- Patient followed up after two weeks with improved CBC and symptom free.
Report attached

MRN / PIN: C-2-58617 / 2002-01-014968 Age/Gender: 22 yr(s)/M
Ref. By: Dr. AKIF Dilshad Ref.No: ECL0PD

Visit Date: 06-Feb-2020 2:09 pm **Final Report** Report Date: 18-Feb-2020 2:02 pm

Test Name	Results	*Last Available Results	Unit	Reference Ranges
Hematology				
Complete Blood Picture (CBC)	06-Feb-2020	20-Jan-2020	14-Jan-2020	
WBC Count	8,000	9,600	10,500 /mm ³	4000 - 11,000
RBC Count	6.88	6.94	6.63 mil/mm ³	4.5-6.0
Haemoglobin	15.9	16.1	15.9 g/dL	14.0 - 18.0
Hematocrit	53	54	52 %	40 - 50
MCV	78	78	78 fl	80 - 95
MCH	23	23	24 pg	27 - 31
MCHC	30	30	30 g/dL	32 - 36
RDW-CV	16	16	16 %	11 - 16
Platelet Count	669,200**	910,100	848,800 /mm ³	140,000 - 425,000
Differential Count				
Neutrophils	55	56	61 %	50 - 70
Lymphocytes	27	27	19 %	25 - 40
Monocytes	10	11	13 %	2 - 10
Eosinophils	08	06	07 %	0 - 4
Bands	00	00	00 %	0 - 5
Absolute Count				
Absolute Neutrophil Count	4420	5383	6405 /mm ³	2500-7000
Absolute Lymphocyte Count	1846	2406	2026 /mm ³	1500-4000
Absolute Monocyte Count	809	1017	1344 /mm ³	200-1000
Absolute Eosinophil Count	665	566	709 /mm ³	100-500
Reticulocytes Count	1.5		%	Adults: 0.5 - 1.5 New Born: 2.5 - 6.5

Thrombocytosis.

** Result has been rechecked from slide. Please correlate clinically.

Please Note: Test (s) are performed on state - of - the - art Cell Dyn Ruby, automated 5 part hematology analyzer from Abbott Diagnostics, USA.

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